

Mercerization Treatment Parameter Effect on Natural Fiber Reinforced Polymer Matrix Composite: A Brief Review

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Abstract—Environmental awareness and depletion of the petroleum resources are among vital factors that motivate a number of researchers to explore the potential of reusing natural fiber as an alternative composite material in industries such as packaging, automotive and building constructions. Natural fibers are available in abundance, low cost, lightweight polymer composite and most importance its biodegradability features, which often called “eco-friendly” materials. However, their applications are still limited due to several factors like moisture absorption, poor wettability and large scattering in mechanical properties. Among the main challenges on natural fibers reinforced matrices composite is their inclination to entangle and form fibers agglomerates during processing due to fiber-fiber interaction. This tends to prevent better dispersion of the fibers into the matrix, resulting in poor interfacial adhesion between the hydrophobic matrix and the hydrophilic reinforced natural fiber. Therefore, to overcome this challenge, fiber treatment process is one common alternative that can be used to modify the fiber surface topology by chemically, physically or mechanically technique. Nevertheless, this paper attempt to focus on the effect of mercerization treatment on mechanical properties enhancement of natural fiber reinforced composite or so-called bio composite. It specifically discussed on mercerization parameters, and natural fiber reinforced composite mechanical properties enhancement.

Keywords—Mercerization treatment, mechanical properties, natural fiber and bio composite

I. INTRODUCTION

THE use of natural fibers as reinforced material in composite manufacturing was incredibly increased due to environmental awareness, depletion of non-renewable petroleum resource and growing demand on sustainable product development [1-3]. A tremendous number of publications over the past two decades have agreed that natural fibers give competent potential to be used as an alternate for glass or other's man made synthetic fiber reinforcement materials in composites [4-9].

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The applications is diversified into the engineering end uses mainly for non structural applications such as in interior lining for automotive component [10-11], packaging materials [12], insulation [13-14], acoustic absorption panel [15-16] and building materials [17-18]. These eco friendly materials have various interesting properties, which make it an attractive and comparable to traditional synthetic reinforced material. Some of natural fiber advantages are abundantly available, inexpensive, low density, high specific stiffness and strength, lightweight, desirable fiber aspect ratio, minimal health hazards, non-abrasive, outstanding insulation properties, enhanced energy recovery, renewability and biodegradability [19-22]. However, although natural fiber reinforced composite seem to give a promising benefit as compare to synthetic fiber, there are still several critical issues need to be addressed before manufacturing industry gains full confidence to enable wide-scale acceptance of this material in a global market. The shape, size and strength of the natural plant fibers may vary widely depending on cultivation environment, geographical origin, plant maturity, retting technique, and composite manufacturing process [23-24].

The numerous highlight problem in dealing with natural fiber was it hydrophilic nature, which leads to an adhesion problem with hydrophobic nature of the polymer matrix [23]. Hydrophilic character of natural fibers is incompatible with hydrophobic polymer matrix and has a tendency to form aggregates. Furthermore, it exhibit poor resistant to moisture, which lead to high water absorption, subsequently resulting in poor mechanical properties and dimensional stability of the natural fiber reinforced composites [24-25]. Therefore, chemical modifications either on natural fiber, polymer matrix or both materials are an alternative solution to overcome these challenges [26-30]. The chemical modification is attempted to improve natural fiber hydrophobic nature, interfacial bonding between matrix and fiber, surface roughness and wettability, and also decrease moisture absorption, leading to the enhancement of mechanical properties of the natural fiber reinforced composites [8, 31]. Mercerization is a common fiber treatment that extensively used by the number of researcher [32-35]. However, for various types of fiber, distinct mercerization treatment conditions were used, and very limited paper took a partial review on these condition interaction effects on fiber and it composite properties enhancement.

Thus, the aim of this paper is to briefly review the mercerization parameter's effect on natural fiber and its composite mechanical properties enhancement. The mercerization parameters that will be stressed in this paper are sodium hydroxide (NaOH) concentration, temperature and soaking duration. This paper also attempts to discuss the interaction of mercerization parameter's interaction toward mechanical properties enhancement of natural fiber reinforced composite. The next section of this paper will briefly describe the mercerization treatment. Section three discussed the common mercerization treatment conditions. The following section is about properties enhancement via mercerization treatment. The conclusion of this work and the recommendation for future work will be highlighted at conclusion section.

II. MERCERIZATION TREATMENT

Mercerization is an alkali treatment process. It is widely used in textile industry [36]. The standard definition of mercerization as proposed by ASTM D1965 is: the process of subjecting a vegetable fiber to an interaction with a fairly concentrated aqueous solution of strong base, to produce great swelling with resultant changes in the fine structure, dimension, morphology and mechanical properties [1]. Therefore, mercerization is a chemical modification process that changed the chemical constituent behavior in natural fiber. The effect of alkali on cellulose fiber is a swelling reaction, during which the natural crystalline structure of the cellulose relaxes. The schematic illustration of the swelling process in cellulose is shown in Fig. 1 [37]. Native cellulose (i.e. cellulose as it occurs in nature) shows a monoclinic crystalline lattice of cellulose-I, which can be changed into different polymorphous forms through chemical or thermal treatments. The important forms of alkali-cellulose and cellulose-II are shown in Fig. 2 [21].

Fig. 1 schematic illustration of the swelling process in cellulose [37]

Fig. 2 Lattice structure of cellulose I and cellulose II [21]

The type of alkali and its concentration will influence the degree of swelling, and hence the degree of lattice transformation into cellulose-II. It has been reported that Na^+ has got a favorable diameter, able to widen the smallest pores in between the lattice planes and penetrate into them. Consequently, sodium hydroxide (NaOH) treatment results in a higher amount of swelling. This leads to the formation of new Na-cellulose-I lattice, a lattice with relatively large distances between the cellulose molecules, and these spaces are filled with H_2O molecules. In this structure, the OH-groups of the cellulose are converted into O - Na-groups, expanding the dimensions of molecules. Subsequent rinsing with water will remove the linked Na-ions and convert the cellulose to a new crystalline structure, i.e. cellulose-II, which is thermodynamically more stable than cellulose-I. NaOH can cause a complete lattice transformation from cellulose-I to cellulose-II. Addition of aqueous sodium hydroxide (NaOH) to natural fiber promotes the ionization of the hydroxyl group to the alkoxide. The following reaction takes place as a result of alkali treatment [26, 37-38]:

As reported in much literature, natural fiber chemical constituent consists of cellulose and other non cellulose constituent like hemicellulose, lignin, pectin and impurities such as wax, ash and natural oil [39-40]. This non cellulose material could be removed by appropriate alkali treatments, which affect the tensile characteristic of the fiber [38, 41]. Mercerization was found to change fiber surface topography, and the fiber diameter was reported to be decreased with increased concentration of sodium hydroxide concentration [42]. Mercerization treatment also results in surface modifications leading to increase wettability of coir fiber polyester resin as reported by Prasad et. al [43]. It is reported in that alkaline treatment has two effects on the henequen fiber: (1) it increases surface roughness, resulting in better mechanical interlocking; and (2) it increases the amount of cellulose exposed on the fiber surface, thus increasing the number of possible reaction sites [44]. Consequently, alkaline treatment has a lasting effect on the mechanical behavior of natural fibers, especially on their strength and stiffness.

III. TREATMENT CONDITIONS

An excellent discussion of mercerization effects and its observed behavior was reported by Symington et. al [45]. They highlight two important mercerization treatments, which are NaOH concentration and processing time could increase 30% in interfacial strength in composite with a proper pre-treatment process. The general concentration ranges of NaOH seem to be 1-25% and processing time of 1-60 minute.

However, in real application, due to chemical constituent variation among similar types or different types of natural fiber, optimal mercerization conditions like NaOH concentration, time and temperature will vary for each fiber. Norazawa et. al study the effect of alkali treatment on kenaf – Ecoflex composites mechanical properties. The composite was prepared to use different fiber loading, and the fiber was treated with various concentrations of NaOH solution. They're found that 40% fiber loading improved the tensile strength

TABLE I
GATHERED COMMON MERCERIZATION TREATMENT PARAMETERS FROM LITERATURE

Natural Fiber	Matrix	NaOH Treatment Parameters			Effect/Comments	Ref.
		Concentration %	Temp. (°C)	Duration		
Pineapple, sisal	Polyester	5 & 10 %	30	1 h	At 10% NaOH, excess delignification occurred. Thus, fiber become weaker	[46]
Sisal	Polyester	0.25,0.5,1.0, 2.0, 5.0 & 10% w/w	Room temperature	1 h	NaOH treatment decrease fiber density. 10% treatment results a rougher surface than untreated	[47]
Hemp & kenaf	Polyester	6 %	19 ± 2	48 h	Cell wall densification identification from small positive change in fiber density observation	[48]
Curaua	Biodegradable resin	5, 10 & 15wt %	Room temperature	1 h & 2 h	Decrease of fiber diameter, fiber weight, fiber density and tensile strength with increasing NaOH content	[49]
Henequen	HDPE	2% w/v	25	1 h	Surface modification increase the area of contact and further expose the cellulose microfibril. Thus, improve fiber wetting and impregnation	[50]
Kenaf	-	3, 6 & 9%	Room temperature and 95°C for 6% NaOH	3 h	3% NaOH was ineffective to remove impurities on fiber surface, 9% NaOH show cleanest fiber surface	[51]
Pineapple	-	2% w/v	95	2 h	Decrease in tensile strength and Young modulus were probably due to decrease in the degree of crystallinity and crystallite orientation	[52]
Kenaf, Flax & Hemp	Epoxy	5%	Room temperature	1 h	NaOH treated kenaf and hemp composite absorb more water than silane only or alkali and silane treated samples	[23]
Sisal & Oil palm	Natural rubber	0.5, 1, 2 & 4%	Ambient temperature	1 h	Alkali treated composite exhibited better tensile properties than silane treated composite	[24]
Coir	Polypropylene	2, 4, 6, 8 & 10%	Room temperature	4 week	Denser NaOH solution provided more Na ⁺ and OH ⁻ ions to react with the substances on the fiber, causing greater amount of lignin, pectin, fatty acid and the cellulose to leach out, this would be detrimental to the fiber strength.	[53]
Ramie	PLA	5% w/v	Room temperature	3 h	Alkali treated composite exhibited better tensile properties than silane treated composite	[54]
Hemp	PLA	5%	Ambient temperature	30 min	Show higher tensile strength (75.5MPa) and Young modulus (8.2GPa)	[55]

properties and whole stem kenaf fiber treated with 4% NaOH was found to enhance composite tensile and flexural properties compared with untreated fiber [56]. Umar et. al reported that 4% NaOH could clean the impurities and make a Betelnut fiber surface a bit rougher [57]. When NaOH concentration increased to 6%, they're found that Betelnut fiber became totally free from any impurities.

Table I expressed a literature summary stress on mercerization treatment parameters focused on NaOH concentration, processing temperature and soaking duration. From Table 1, it shows a number of researches were conducted to determine the optimum NaOH solution concentration during the mercerization process at specific soaking duration and/or soaking temperature. However, there are limited work reported regarding attempts to determine the main effect and the interaction between these three factors on it effect to natural fiber and its final composite mechanical properties performance.

IV. PROPERTIES ENHANCEMENT

When dealing with natural fiber reinforce composite, generally there will have two stages of performance evaluation. First, is the natural fiber characteristic evaluation [58-59] and secondly is the fabricated composite evaluation [60]. Most of the literature were focused on both stages which considering some modification on the fiber [61] or polymer matrix [62] and finally evaluate the final composite performance which generally fabricated with variation of fiber matrix mixing ratio. There are tremendous research conducted to evaluate performance of natural fiber and it reinforced composite [18, 21, 23, 63-65]. This performance evaluation is mostly depending on composite characterization determination and presented in terms of physical, mechanical and thermal properties. These characteristics are important to determine material ability, especially under extreme and critical conditions, which are directly connected with engineering performance.

TABLE II
MERCERIZATION TREATMENT EFFECT ON POLYMER COMPOSITE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Natural Fiber	Matrix	Fiber Properties		Polymer Composite Properties			Effect / Comments	Ref.
		Shear Strength (MPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Impact Strength (KJ/m ²)		
Sisal	Polyester	6.9 at 2% NaOH	375.4 at 2% NaOH	-	-	-	Sisal surface smoother at NaOH less than 2%, rougher when more than 5%	[47]
Hemp & kenaf	Polyester	-	-	-	Treated long fiber > Treated short fiber > untreated fiber	Untreated hemp polyester composite show greater work of fracture value	Flexural strength depends on fiber alignment and resin rich areas location	[48]
Curaua	Bio-degradable resin	-	Decreased for treated fiber compared to untreated fiber	Treated =137 Untreated = 124 (slightly higher) [49]	-	-	2 factors contribute to composite tensile strength: 1: Interfacial bonding improvement, 2: Decrease in the coefficient of variation of alkali treated fiber strength	[49, 66]
Kenaf	-	-	6% NaOH at 95 ^o C is 243.7	-	-	-	9% NaOH was too strong and might damage the fibers, thus resulting lower tensile strength	[51]

Natural Fiber	Matrix	Fiber Properties		Polymer Composite Properties			Effect / Comments	Ref.
		Shear Strength (MPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Impact Strength (KJ/m ²)		
Sisal	Polyester	6.9 at 2% NaOH	375.4 at 2% NaOH	-	-	-	Sisal surface smoother at NaOH less than 2%, rougher when more than 5%	[47]
Hemp	Poly-propylene & MAPP	-	347 at 10 wt%, Young modulus = 20.3 GPa	Increase with the increase of MAPP content	-	-	Alkali treatment separate the fiber bundles into elementary fiber by degrading the cementing material	[67]
Ramie	PLA	-	-	66.8±1.7	170	24	Alkali treatment seem to be an effective surface treatment agent compare to silane	[54]
Jute	-	Increase 50% (370±134MPa) compare to untreated fiber	-	-	-	-	Fiber diameter decrease due to the removal of hemicellulose, pectin and lignin	[68]
Basalt	Un-saturated Polyester	Up 2.23% from untreated	-	Increased 11.85% compared to untreated	-	Increased 9.58% compared to untreated	Basalt fiber reinforced composites performance was superior to the glass fiber reinforced composites	[69]
Sugar Cane / Bagasse	PVC	-	-	25	-	-	Untreated SB/PVC composite showed higher tensile strength compared to chemically treated fiber	[70]
Kenaf	Epoxy	-	-	-	Alkali treated show 36% strength increment	-	Improvement on the interfacial adhesion of the fibers and the porosity of the composites was increased the flexural strength	[71]

These characteristics are important to determine material ability, especially under extreme and critical conditions, which are directly connected with engineering performance. In this short review, the focused was zoomed in mercerization parameters effect on natural fiber physical properties and its reinforced composite mechanical properties. The mercerization effect on common mechanical properties of several natural fibers and it composite commonly was highlight in Table 2. Table 2 highlighted the properties of natural fiber and it fiber reinforced polymer composite. In fiber stage, the stressed properties were fiber-matrix interfacial shear strength and fiber tensile properties. For composite stage, the mechanical properties like tensile strength, flexural strength and impact strength was reviewed.

V.CONCLUSIONS

This review paper has considered significant used of the mercerization treatment process in natural fiber reinforced polymer matrix composite. The text addressed the mercerization parameters (sodium hydroxide (NaOH) concentration, temperature and soaking duration) effect on properties enhancement of it composite. However, due to the large variety in natural fiber types which effect it chemical composition, the treatment condition also found to be different according to the selected reinforced fiber. As a conclusion from this brief review, the following issues could be highlighted for further understanding the mercerization treatment conditions effect on natural fiber reinforced polymer composite mechanical properties enhancement.

- Mercerization or alkali treatment is one of the common techniques that widely used for modification of fiber surface. Furthermore, this treatment was considered as a simplest and cheapest treatment method compared to other chemical treatment methods.
- In this brief review, it was clearly shown that although tremendous research results were published regarding natural fiber mercerization treatment, there are still scant works conducted in dealing with interaction and optimizing the mercerization treatment conditions.
- It was found that the most parameters used in mercerization treatment were alkali concentration, fiber soaking temperature and fiber soaking duration. Although similar types of reinforced fiber are used, it could give different values in its final composite mechanical properties due to different parameter setting during a mercerization treatment process.
- Therefore, there is a significant need to conduct further work focusing on main effect and interaction effect of mercerization parameters setting toward enhancement of natural fiber reinforce composite mechanical properties.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. K. Bledzki and J. Gassan, "Composites reinforced with cellulose based fibres," *Progress in Polymer Science*, vol. 24, pp. 221-274, 1999.
- [2] M. A. Dweib, *et al.*, "All natural composite sandwich beams for structural applications," *Composite Structures*, vol. 63, pp. 147-157, 2004.
- [3] N. Graupner, *et al.*, "Natural and man-made cellulose fibre-reinforced poly(lactic acid) (PLA) composites: An overview about mechanical characteristics and application areas," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 40, pp. 810-821, 2009.
- [4] S. J. Eichhorn, *et al.*, "Review: Current international research into cellulosic fibres and composites," *Journal of Materials Science*, vol. 36, pp. 2107-2131, 2001.
- [5] S. Eichhorn, *et al.*, "Review: current international research into cellulose nanofibres and nanocomposites," *Journal of Materials Science*, vol. 45, pp. 1-33, 2010.
- [6] J. Summerscales, *et al.*, "A review of bast fibres and their composites. Part 1 - Fibres as reinforcements," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 41, pp. 1329-1335, 2010.
- [7] S. Kalia, *et al.*, "Cellulose-Based Bio- and Nanocomposites: A Review," *International Journal of Polymer Science*, vol. 2011, 2011.
- [8] H. Ku, *et al.*, "A review on the tensile properties of natural fiber reinforced polymer composites," *Composites Part B: Engineering*, vol. 42, pp. 856-873, 2011.
- [9] F. P. La Mantia and M. Morreale, "Green composites: A brief review," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 42, pp. 579-588, 2011.
- [10] J. Holbery and D. Houston, "Natural-fiber-reinforced polymer composites in automotive applications," *JOM Journal of the Minerals, Metals and Materials Society*, vol. 58, pp. 80-86, 2006.
- [11] M. M. Davoodi, *et al.*, "Mechanical properties of hybrid kenaf/glass reinforced epoxy composite for passenger car bumper beam," *Materials & Design*, vol. 31, pp. 4927-4932, 2010.
- [12] S. N. Chaudhary, *et al.*, "Sunhemp Fiber-reinforced Waste Polyethylene Bag Composites," *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, vol. 29, pp. 2241-2252, August 1, 2010.
- [13] H.-R. Kymäläinen and A.-M. Sjöberg, "Flax and hemp fibres as raw materials for thermal insulations," *Building and Environment*, vol. 43, pp. 1261-1269, 2008.
- [14] X.-y. Zhou, *et al.*, "An environment-friendly thermal insulation material from cotton stalk fibers," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 42, pp. 1070-1074, 2010.
- [15] C. Koenig, *et al.*, "Acoustical Parameters of Automotive Interiors using Hybrid Fleeces basing on natural fibres," *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, vol. 123, p. 3675, 2008.
- [16] M. Hosseini Fouladi, *et al.*, "Utilization of coir fiber in multilayer acoustic absorption panel," *Applied Acoustics*, vol. 71, pp. 241-249, 2010.
- [17] A. Elsaid, *et al.*, "Mechanical properties of kenaf fiber reinforced concrete," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 25, pp. 1991-2001, 2011.
- [18] N. J. Rodríguez, *et al.*, "Assessment of coconut fibre insulation characteristics and its use to modulate temperatures in concrete slabs with the aid of a finite element methodology," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 43, pp. 1264-1272, 2011.
- [19] S. Joshi, *et al.*, "Are natural fiber composites environmentally superior to glass fiber reinforced composites?," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 35, pp. 371-376, 2004.
- [20] L. Mwaikambo, "Review of the history, properties and application of plant fibres," *African Journal of Science and Technology*, vol. 7, p. 121, 2006.
- [21] M. John and R. Anandjiwala, "Recent developments in chemical modification and characterization of natural fiber reinforced composites," *Polymer composites*, vol. 29, pp. 187-207, 2008.
- [22] K. G. Satyanarayana, *et al.*, "Biodegradable composites based on lignocellulosic fibers--An overview," *Progress in Polymer Science*, vol. 34, pp. 982-1021, 2009.
- [23] N. Sgriccia, *et al.*, "Characterization of natural fiber surfaces and natural fiber composites," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 39, pp. 1632-1637, 2008.
- [24] M. J. John, *et al.*, "Effect of chemical modification on properties of hybrid fiber biocomposites," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 39, pp. 352-363, 2008.
- [25] P. A. Sreekumar, *et al.*, "Effect of fiber surface modification on the mechanical and water absorption characteristics of sisal/polyester composites fabricated by resin transfer molding," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 40, pp. 1777-1784, 2009.
- [26] X. Li, *et al.*, "Chemical Treatments of Natural Fiber for Use in Natural Fiber-Reinforced Composites: A Review," *Journal of Polymers and the Environment*, vol. 15, pp. 25-33, 2007.
- [27] V. Vilay, *et al.*, "Effect of fiber surface treatment and fiber loading on the properties of bagasse fiber-reinforced unsaturated polyester composites," *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 68, pp. 631-638, 2008.
- [28] S. Kalia, *et al.*, "Pretreatments of natural fibers and their application as reinforcing material in polymer composites—A review," *Polymer Engineering & Science*, vol. 49, pp. 1253-1272, 2009.
- [29] Y. Xie, *et al.*, "Silane coupling agents used for natural fiber/polymer composites: A review," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 41, pp. 806-819, 2010.
- [30] I. M. De Rosa, *et al.*, "Effect of chemical treatments on the mechanical and thermal behaviour of okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus*) fibres," *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 71, pp. 246-254, 2011.
- [31] J. George, *et al.*, "A review on interface modification and characterization of natural fiber reinforced plastic composites," *Polymer Engineering & Science*, vol. 41, pp. 1471-1485, 2001.
- [32] D. Bachtiar, *et al.*, "The effect of alkaline treatment on tensile properties of sugar palm fibre reinforced epoxy composites," *Materials & Design*, vol. 29, pp. 1285-1290, 2008.
- [33] M. S. Islam, *et al.*, "Influence of alkali treatment on the interfacial and physico-mechanical properties of industrial hemp fibre reinforced polylactic acid composites," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 41, pp. 596-603, 2010.
- [34] H. M. Akil, *et al.*, "Kenaf Fiber Reinforced Composites: A Review," *Materials & Design*, vol. Volume 32, September 2011, pp. Pages 4107-4121 2011.

- [35] D. Cho, *et al.*, "Effect of alkali pre-treatment of jute on the formation of jute-based carbon fibers," *Materials Letters*, vol. 65, pp. 1492-1494, 2011.
- [36] H. M. Wang, *et al.*, "Removing Pectin and Lignin During Chemical Processing of Hemp for Textile Applications," *Textile Research Journal*, 2003.
- [37] L. Y. Mwaikambo and M. P. Ansell, "Chemical modification of hemp, sisal, jute, and kapok fibers by alkalization," *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, vol. 84, pp. 2222-2234, 2002.
- [38] S. Sreenivasan, *et al.*, "Influence of delignification and alkali treatment on the fine structure of coir fibres," *Journal of Materials Science*, vol. 31, pp. 721-726, 1996.
- [39] H. Khalil, *et al.*, "Chemical composition, anatomy, lignin distribution, and cell wall structure of Malaysian plant waste fibers," *BioResources*, vol. 1, 2006.
- [40] H. P. S. Abdul Khalil, *et al.*, "Cell wall ultrastructure, anatomy, lignin distribution, and chemical composition of Malaysian cultivated kenaf fiber," *Industrial Crops and Products*, vol. 31, pp. 113-121, 2010.
- [41] J. Gassan and A. K. Bledzki, "Possibilities for improving the mechanical properties of jute/epoxy composites by alkali treatment of fibres," *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 59, pp. 1303-1309, 1999.
- [42] L. Y. Mwaikambo and M. Ansell, "Mechanical properties of alkali treated plant fibres and their potential as reinforcement materials. I. hemp fibres," *Journal of Materials Science*, vol. 41, pp. 2483-2496, 2006.
- [43] S. V. Prasad, *et al.*, "Alkali treatment of coir fibres for coir-polyester composites," *Journal of Materials Science*, vol. 18, pp. 1443-1454, 1983.
- [44] A. Valadez-Gonzalez, *et al.*, "Effect of fiber surface treatment on the fiber-matrix bond strength of natural fiber reinforced composites," *Composites Part B: Engineering*, vol. 30, pp. 309-320, 1999.
- [45] M. C. Symington, *et al.*, "Tensile Testing of Cellulose Based Natural Fibers for Structural Composite Applications," *Journal of Composite Materials*, vol. 43, pp. 1083-1108, May 1, 2009 2009.
- [46] S. Mishra, *et al.*, "Studies on mechanical performance of biofibre/glass reinforced polyester hybrid composites," *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 63, pp. 1377-1385, 2003.
- [47] T. H. D. Sydenstricker, *et al.*, "Pull-out and other evaluations in sisal-reinforced polyester biocomposites," *Polymer Testing*, vol. 22, pp. 375-380, 2003.
- [48] S. H. Aziz and M. P. Ansell, "The effect of alkalization and fibre alignment on the mechanical and thermal properties of kenaf and hemp bast fibre composites: Part 1 - polyester resin matrix," *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 64, pp. 1219-1230, 2004.
- [49] A. Gomes, *et al.*, "Effects of alkali treatment to reinforcement on tensile properties of curaua fiber green composites," *JSME International Journal Series A*, vol. 47, pp. 541-546, 2004.
- [50] P. J. Herrera-Franco and A. Valadez-González, "A study of the mechanical properties of short natural-fiber reinforced composites," *Composites Part B: Engineering*, vol. 36, pp. 597-608, 2005.
- [51] A. M. M. Edeerozey, *et al.*, "Chemical modification of kenaf fibers," *Materials Letters*, vol. 61, pp. 2023-2025, 2007.
- [52] S. Munawar, *et al.*, "Effects of alkali, mild steam, and chitosan treatments on the properties of pineapple, ramie, and sansevieria fiber bundles," *Journal of Wood Science*, vol. 54, pp. 28-35, 2008.
- [53] H. Gu, "Tensile behaviours of the coir fibre and related composites after NaOH treatment," *Materials & Design*, vol. 30, pp. 3931-3934, 2009.
- [54] T. Yu, *et al.*, "Effect of fiber surface-treatments on the properties of poly(lactic acid)/ramie composites," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 41, pp. 499-505, 2010.
- [55] M. A. Sawpan, *et al.*, "Improvement of mechanical performance of industrial hemp fibre reinforced polylactide biocomposites," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 42, pp. 310-319, 2011.
- [56] Nor Azowa Ibrahim, *et al.*, "Effect of Fiber Treatment on Mechanical Properties of Kenaf Fiber-Ecoflex Composites," *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, vol. 29, pp. 2192-2198, July 1, 2010 2010.
- [57] U. Nirmal, *et al.*, "On the effect of different polymer matrix and fibre treatment on single fibre pullout test using betelnut fibres," *Materials & Design*, vol. 32, pp. 2717-2726, 2011.
- [58] N. Defoirdt, *et al.*, "Assessment of the tensile properties of coir, bamboo and jute fibre," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 41, pp. 588-595, 2010.
- [59] M. Aslan, *et al.*, "Strength variability of single flax fibres," *Journal of Materials Science*, vol. 46, pp. 6344-6354, 2011.
- [60] C. Asasutjarit, *et al.*, "Materials and mechanical properties of pretreated coir-based green composites," *Composites Part B: Engineering*, vol. 40, pp. 633-637, 2009.
- [61] S. H. P. Bettini, *et al.*, "Investigation on the use of coir fiber as alternative reinforcement in polypropylene," *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, vol. 118, pp. 2841-2848, 2010.
- [62] S. Rassmann, *et al.*, "Effect of resin system on the mechanical properties and water absorption of kenaf fibre reinforced laminates," *Materials & Design*, vol. 32, pp. 1399-1406, 2011.
- [63] A. Alawar, *et al.*, "Characterization of treated date palm tree fiber as composite reinforcement," *Composites Part B: Engineering*, vol. 40, pp. 601-606, 2009.
- [64] S. Shinoj, *et al.*, "Towards industrial utilization of oil palm fibre: Physical and dielectric characterization of linear low density polyethylene composites and comparison with other fibre sources," *Biosystems Engineering*, vol. 106, pp. 378-388, 2010.
- [65] O. Shinji, "Mechanical properties of kenaf fibers and kenaf/PLA composites," *Mechanics of Materials*, vol. 40, pp. 446-452, 2008 2008.
- [66] A. Gomes, *et al.*, "Development and effect of alkali treatment on tensile properties of curaua fiber green composites," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 38, pp. 1811-1820, 2007.
- [67] G. W. Beckermann and K. L. Pickering, "Engineering and evaluation of hemp fibre reinforced polypropylene composites: Fibre treatment and matrix modification," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 39, pp. 979-988, 2008.
- [68] P. Saha, *et al.*, "Enhancement of tensile strength of lignocellulosic jute fibers by alkali-steam treatment," *Bioresource Technology*, vol. 101, pp. 3182-3187, 2010.
- [69] V. Manikandan, *et al.*, "Investigation of the effect of surface modifications on the mechanical properties of basalt fibre reinforced polymer composites," *Composites Part B: Engineering*, vol. 43, pp. 812-818, 2012.
- [70] R. Wirawan, *et al.*, "Properties of sugarcane bagasse/ poly(vinyl chloride) composites after various treatments," *Journal of Composite Materials*, vol. 45, pp. 1667-1674, August 1, 2011 2011.
- [71] B. F. Yousif, *et al.*, "Flexural properties of treated and untreated kenaf/epoxy composites," *Materials & Design*, vol. 40, pp. 378-385, 2012.